

HCl medium : (1.0M) : NV, NR, ACG, ACB, WFBGL, CB, SPAS, CLB, GB and MB.

H₂SO₄ medium : (1.0M) + 5 ml of 10% KBr solution : NV, NR, WFBGL, CLB, SPAS and GB

NG does not function satisfactorily in any acid medium.

Titrations of 0.1N solutions do not require any indicator correction whereas those involving 0.01N solutions require the following indicator corrections :

HCl medium : NV, NR, ACG, ACB and WFBGL : 0.02 ml ; CB : 0.04 ml ; GB : 0.06 ml ; SPAS, CLB and MB : 0.10 ml

H₂SO₄ medium : NV, NR, WFBGL and CLB : 0.04 ml ; SPAS and GB : 0.10 ml.

Reverse titrations : Variamine blue⁷ is the only indicator proposed for the reverse titrations, i. e., titrations of potassium bromate with ascorbic acid. Our investigations have shown that ACG, ACB and WFBGL can be satisfactorily employed in the titrations of potassium bromate with ascorbic acid in 1.5 - 1.75M sulphuric acid medium. In these titrations, the indicator has to be added towards the close of the titration, and waiting for about 30-40 sec is necessary in the vicinity of the end point. The end point is taken as that at which the colour of the dye, pink with ACG and ACB and blue with WFBGL, is imparted to the titration mixture and is stable for more than 30 sec.

Attempts to perform the reverse titrations in hydrochloric acid medium yielded erratic results.

Mechanism of indicator action ; The functioning of the indicators in these titrations can be explained to be due to the bromination of the dye indicators, in view of the liberation of bromine and discharge of the colours of the dyes at the end points. Separate experiments have indicated that these dyes get decolourised by bromination. Further support to this mechanism is provided by the work of Bogner⁸ involving the use of the azine dyes, Azocarmine B, Azocarmine BX, Azocarmine G, Azocarmine GX, Rosindulin G, Rosindulin GG, and Rosindulin 2G, as indicators in the titration of arsenic (III) and antimony (III) with a solution of bromine.

In view of the advantages associated with the use of the azine and oxazine dye indicators in the bromatometric titrations of ascorbic acid, we have applied the methods now developed for the determination of ascorbic acid content of commercial vitamin C tablets. Solutions of the tablets were prepared as described in an earlier method⁹ and aliquots of the solutions were titrated with 0.1N potassium bromate solution using any one of the azine and oxazine dye indicators. A similar aliquot was titrated using *p*-ethoxychrysoidine as indicator as

per the method of Schulek *et al*¹. Typical results obtained are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1 - DETERMINATION OF ASCORBIC ACID IN VITAMIN C TABLETS

Indicator and amount of ascorbic acid found, in g, in 6 tablets ^φ		
Schulek's method ¹	ACG ^α	SPAS ^α
2.95 ± 0.01	2.95 ± 0.01	2.95 ± 0.01
2.97 ± 0.01	2.98 ± 0.01	2.98 ± 0.01
3.10 ± 0.01	3.09 ± 0.01	3.10 ± 0.01
2.94 ± 0.01	2.94 ± 0.01	2.93 ± 0.01

^φ These were market products of different manufacturers.
^α Similar results were obtained with the remaining nine indicators also.

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Spectrophotometric Microgram Determination of Lead

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EXTENSIVE work on the determination of lead present as contamination has been carried out by various workers¹⁻⁴. Lead as usual with other metals becomes toxic in nature beyond certain conce-

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centration level in a variety of food stuffs. The conventional methods followed for determination of lead in food stuffs, comprise visual comparative colour developments with ammonium acetate, potassium cyanide and sodium sulphide or hydrogen sulphide in ammoniacal medium. However, these methods lack precision due to personal error. In this communication, an improved and precise method for determining lead in trace amounts by absorbance measurement, after eliminating the interfering inorganic and organic materials by standard methods is described.

Materials and Method :

Materials : All chemicals used were of AR grade. Carl Zeiss VSU2-P spectrophotometer was used for measuring the absorbance. Doubly distilled water over alkaline potassium permanganate in all glass apparatus was used throughout the experiments.

Procedure : Lead as lead nitrate was allowed to form a brown complex with potassium cyanide (1 ml, 10%) and sodium sulphide (0.5 ml, 10%) in ammoniacal medium (3 ml. ammonia, sp. gr. 0.91). The absorbance of which was recorded after diluting the contents to 50 ml. with water at 290 nm. Lead from 1-12 μ g per ml was found to obey Beer's Law. The amount of lead determined was computed from a standard calibration curve. Blank experiments were also carried out simultaneously under similar identical conditions. The results are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF LEAD

Lead (μ g)		Absorbance*	% Error
Taken Per ml.	Found Per ml.		
1.00	0.98	0.068	-2.00
1.50	1.52	0.10	+1.33
2.00	1.97	0.130	-1.50
3.00	3.03	0.20	+1.00
4.00	4.02	0.264	+ .50
6.00	6.02	0.382	+0.33
8.00	7.92	0.53	-1.00
9.00	8.91	0.585	-1.00
10.00	10.15	0.65	+1.50
12.00	12.15	0.90	+1.25

* Mean of five determinations.

All the studies were made at wavelength 290 nm and slit width 0.3 mm.

Total volume of the complex solution was always raised to 50 ml. in all the experiments.

Results and Discussion

From the observations, it is evident that the method developed may be suitable for determining lead contents in food stuffs in p.p.m. level after eliminating interfering materials. Various experiments performed show that excess of potassium cyanide (10ml, 10%), ammonia (10 ml, sp. gr. 0.91) and sodium sulphide (1 ml. 10%) have practically no effect on the absorbance of the lead complex.

It has, however, been noted that the complex decomposes on standing, and thus it is suggested that absorbance should be measured immediately after the complex formation or within 10-20 minutes.

An attempt was made to replace sodium sulphide by water saturated with hydrogen sulphide, which met with no success.

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Polarographic Behaviour of *Cis-Trans* Isomers of Platinum(II) Complex of the Type $[\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)(\text{NO}_2)\text{Cl}_2]^-$

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THE ligand arrangement around an atom after a substitution reaction may or may not be similar to that of the starting material even for inert complexes. The chemistry of Platinum(II) is exceptional in this respect, in that the product of a substitution reaction can be predicted with confidence. The *Cis* and *Trans* isomers of Platinum (II) complex having formula $[\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)(\text{NO}_2)\text{Cl}_2]$ have been prepared and examined polarographically. It is observed that each of the isomers gives a separate reversible cathodic polarographic wave. The value of $E_{0.5}$ for *cis*-isomer = -0.105V, Vs SCE and that for *trans*-isomer = -0.140V Vs SCE. In both the cases 1M KCl is used as supporting electrolyte.

Platinum(II) is a very well known ion for the formation of *cis-trans* isomers. In the case of Platinum(II) the product of a substitution reaction can be predicted with confidence.